

A recommender system for supporting students in Programming Online Judges

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Abstract Programming Online Judges (POJs) are tools that contain a large collection of programming problems to be solved by students as a component of their training and programming practices. This contribution presents a recommendation approach to suggest to students the more suitable problems to solve for increasing their performance and motivation in POJs. Some key features of the approach are the use of an enriched user-problem matrix that incorporates specific information related to the user performance in the POJ, and the development of a strategy for natural noise management in such matrix. The experimental evaluation shows the improvements of the proposal as compared to previous works.

Key words: Programming online judges, problems recommendation, natural noise management

1 Introduction

Programming online judges (POJs) are e-learning tools that enclose a set of programming problems to be solved by their users, which usually are students in computer science colleges, and include the automatic compilation

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and evaluation processes for the solutions proposed for the mentioned problems. Over the last few years, POJs have been successfully used for training students that participate in ACM-ICPC-like programming contests, and in the systematic practice of programming skills in universities and high schools [10, 11, 17].

Typical POJs present a sequential list of programming exercises that users can select and try to solve [10]. In these applications it is considered that the users with better performance are those that solve the most problems, because it implies a high level of fulfilment. Such growing satisfaction would increase the learners' efforts and performance in problem solutions and programming subjects, according to a basic pedagogical rule ("learners' effort will increase if they are more satisfied") [13], and then users' learning process is enhanced.

In this way, it is important to remark that the learning process in current POJs, based on the previous rule *the more problems solved the better skills acquired* by the students, are far from other e-learning tools such as ITSs or ontology-supported systems.

Additionally, in a similar way to most online information nowadays, novice users in POJs fail to solve problems, because they are not able to select suitable ones according to their level of knowledge, due to the information overload regarding the available exercises. This causes a discouragement in POJ participation, which results in users misplacing all the benefits that POJ could give them.

A typical solution used to mitigate the negative effect of information overload is the development of recommender systems [1]. Such systems are focused on providing users with the information items that best fit their preferences and needs in a search scenario overloaded with possible options. Recommender systems are employed in diverse contexts such as e-commerce, e-learning, tourism, or libraries [1].

This contribution aims at introducing a memory-based collaborative filtering recommendation approach to support students by mitigating information overload in POJs. This is achieved by identifying the problems that they should solve according to their skills to avoid failures and frustration. Such an approach, so-called Natural Noise Programming Judges, (NN-PJ), presents two novel features:

1. The use of an enriched user-problem matrix that facilitates the calculation of closer neighbourhoods and therefore a more accurate recommendation.
2. The incorporation of a data preprocessing step based on the concept of *natural noise management* [4, 12, 19, 20] that detects and corrects anomalous users' behaviours that could affect the recommendation generation.

It is important to remark that although the proposal is developed specifically for POJs, its innovative principles could additionally be used in other e-learning recommendation scenarios related to problem resolution. This proposal is evaluated through a case study on data associated to a real POJ.

The rest of the contribution is structured as follows. Section 2 revises the required background related to programming online judges and e-learning recommender systems for supporting programming subjects. Section 3 presents the proposal for recommending problems to solve in POJs. Section 4 shows an experimental evaluation of the proposal to compare its performance with previous related works. Finally, Section 5 concludes the contribution.

2 Related works

Here, several concepts and previous works about POJs and systems for supporting the learning of programming are reviewed.

2.1 *Programming online judges*

Programming online judges (POJs) are systems that contain a list of programming problems to be solved by the users. Specifically, a usual interaction of the user in the POJ is composed of the following steps:

1. The user chooses a problem in the POJ and tries to solve it.
2. The user uploads his/her solution to the POJ.
3. The POJ evaluates this solution using predefined input-output data. If the expected output of the solution completely matches with the predefined output, then the solution is considered as correct and the problem solved. Otherwise, the user can go to the previous step to propose an alternative solution for the same problem, or go to the initial step to choose a different problem.

There are some research works focused on the use of these applications to support programming subjects [3]. The first use of the term POJs as systems for supporting the automatic evaluation of source codes developed by students as problems resolution was presented by Kurnia et al. [10]. Afterwards, a widely-used system has been Mooshak [11], that supports the programming contest management and could also be used as an online judge. More recently, Verdu et al. [15] presented EduJudge, which aims at expanding the University of Valladolid Online Judge toward an effective platform that integrates Moodle and QUESTOURnament, a competitive e-learning environment. Finally, Wang et al. [17] presented OJPOT, a novel teaching approach that combines online judges and practice oriented programming teaching, which focuses on developing students' practical abilities through programming practices. Beyond these works there are others that, although do not employ the term online judge, are centred on the automatic evaluation of programming problems solutions [3].

2.2 Supporting programming learning

A main application area for recommender systems has always been the e-learning scenarios [9]. This section briefly reviews previous works related to the current e-learning context, which is the recommendation for supporting programming subjects.

In this way, De Oliveira et al. [5] presented a system for recommending “classes” of activities in programming practices, such as “Math operators”, “data types”, “if structure”, or “while structure”. This task is modelled as a multi-label classification approach, where the student’s profile is associated with some of the mentioned “classes”. Previously, Hsiao et al. [8] presented a system to guide students through the suitable questions in a Java programming course. More recently, Vesin et al. [16] described a recommendation module integrated with an intelligent tutoring system for learning programming. Such module focuses on recognizing the students’ learning styles through the use of several domain ontologies for finding access sequences for the activities, which are later used to recommend relevant links and actions during the learning process. Similarly, Ruiz et al. [14] presented a knowledge-based strategy using semantic information represented by ontologies to recommend educational resources in a programming course to provide personalized access to such resources.

Summarizing, the referred works were conceived for specific predetermined scenarios and are highly content dependent beyond the user-learning resource interaction. However, in POJs only the users’ performance when they aim at solving the problems is available. Therefore, the adaptation of most of the referred works to this context is not straightforward.

Recently, however, two researches presented in [18, 21] are the nearest antecedents to the current contribution, given that they are specifically focused on POJs. The proposal introduced in [18] presents a user-based collaborative filtering approach to suggest problems to solve in a POJ. Centred on the same purpose, the work presented in [21] suggests the application of an item-based collaborative filtering approach. However, both approaches are mainly focused on the direct application of a traditional collaborative filtering technique. The proposal uses techniques specifically focused on the POJs scenario.

3 A recommendation approach for programming online judges

This section presents a novel approach for recommending problems to solve in POJs supported by the available information, which is represented by the users’ performance when they try to solve the presented problems.

Such available information, which is the input for the proposal, is represented as a set of triplets $\langle u, p, j \rangle$ that represent a user u attempt to solve a problem p with a judgement in the category j , which can be “accepted” if the problem is successfully solved or “not accepted” in any other case. To formalize the current proposal, this scenario will be represented as the relation $D : (u, p) \rightarrow (n, solved)$, that receives as input a user u and problem p , and returns the amount of times n that the user tries to resolve the problem, and whether at last it was solved.

Figure 1 presents an overview of the approach, which takes as input the relation D and the active user x to retrieve the list of suggested problems to be solved by the user. It is composed of three main phases: extended user-problem matrix building (Section 3.1), extended user-problem matrix preprocessing for natural noise management (Section 3.2), and problems recommendation (Section 3.3). The following sections will describe these phases in further detail.

Fig. 1 The recommendation approach for programming online judges

3.1 Extended user-problem matrix building

In order to apply a memory-based collaborative filtering approach for recommending problems to solve in the online judge, firstly it is used the relation D to build a boolean user-problem matrix M , whose cells are filled with one if the corresponding user solves the corresponding item or zero in other case.

However, the dynamic of the users’ performance in POJs makes that this basic matrix M is not enough to obtain a suitable user similarity that considers user knowledge and abilities. Therefore, instead of the analysis of a simple similarity regarding problems solved or not solved by the users, we propose the enrichment of the matrix M by considering also the number of unsuccessful attempts $(D(u, p).n)$ when the user u tries to solve the problem

p . Such enrichment allows the construction of a new matrix M^* that leads to more accurate similarity calculation and therefore a better recommendation performance.

To implement this strategy, we propose the conversion of the matrix M , that contains the binary user-problem interaction values, into a matrix M^* composed of different interaction values that considers the unsuccessful solution attempts:

- $M^*[u, p] = 0$, when the user u has never tried to solve the problem p .
- $M^*[u, p] = 1$, when the user u has not solved the problem p , and has tried it just few times.
- $M^*[u, p] = 2$, when the user u has not solved the problem p , and has quite a few previous failed attempts.
- $M^*[u, p] = 3$, when the user u solved the problem p , having failed many times beforehand.
- $M^*[u, p] = 4$, when the user u solves the problem p quickly.

Following, equations (1) and (2) formalize such transformation, depending on the thresholds λ_{p1} and λ_{p2} , being the boundary between the few and the many attempts categories in not solved and solved judgements, respectively. In both cases the thresholds are initialized as the average number of failures associated with all users that have attempted to solve the problem p . Equations (3) and (4) formalize such initialization strategies, where NS_p and S_p are respectively the set of users that have not solved and solved the problem p , and v any user in the POJ.

$$M[u, p] = 0 \rightarrow M^*[u, p] = \begin{cases} \mathbf{0}, & \text{if } D(u, p).n = 0 \text{ (no solution attempts)} \\ \mathbf{1}, & \text{if } D(u, p).n \geq \lambda_{p1} \text{ (not solved, with many} \\ & \text{solution attempts)} \\ \mathbf{2}, & \text{if } D(u, p).n > 0 \text{ and } D(u, p).n < \lambda_{p1} \\ & \text{(not solved, with few solution attempts)} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$M[u, p] = 1 \rightarrow M^*[u, p] = \begin{cases} \mathbf{3}, & \text{if } D(u, p).n \geq \lambda_{p2} \text{ (solved with many} \\ & \text{solution attempts)} \\ \mathbf{4}, & \text{if } D(u, p).n < \lambda_{p2} \\ & \text{(solved, with few solution attempts)} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$\lambda_{p1} = \frac{\sum_{v \in NS_p} D(v, p).n}{|NS_p|} \quad (3)$$

$$\lambda_{p2} = \frac{\sum_{v \in S_p} D(v, p).n}{|S_p|} \quad (4)$$

3.2 Preprocessing natural noise in the extended user-problem matrix

Once the enrichment of the binary user-problem matrix is performed, a new transformation step aims at preprocessing inconsistent data associated with the already transformed matrix M^* to improve the recommendations. This transformation is specifically focused on processing data erroneously related to the users' behaviour, i.e., natural noise [19].

Specifically in e-learning scenarios, it has been pointed out that sometimes the users do not know the solution of the activities, but supposed them correctly; and in contrast, sometimes they recognize their solutions, but make an error [9]. This referred work pointed out that this unexpected behaviour should be regarded in the management of user data in POJs. Considering this scenario and the features associated to natural noise [19], it can be established that these anomalies could be identified as natural noise.

Using such works as a basis, natural noise in the POJ context is characterized as the circumstances where the user does not solve an exercise using the expected predictable effort, which could be occasioned by causes such as plagiarism, guessing, or unexpected slip-ups.

To manage such inconsistent behaviours in the enriched matrix M^* , we suggest the grouping of the problems solved by user u , i.e., those belonging to the categories $M^*[u, p] = 3$ and $M^*[u, p] = 4$, in two sets:

1. Set of problems solved by the user u that needed too many attempts, $C1_u$:
 $C1_u = \{p \mid M^*[u, p] = 3\}$.
2. Set of problems solved by the user u that needed few attempts, $C2_u$:
 $C2_u = \{p \mid M^*[u, p] = 4\}$.

Similarly, the users that solved the problem p are grouped in two sets:

1. Set of users that solved the problem p that needed too many attempts, $C1_p$:
 $C1_p = \{u \mid M^*[u, p] = 3\}$.
2. Set of users that solved the problem p that needed few attempts, $C2_p$:
 $C2_p = \{u \mid M^*[u, p] = 4\}$.

Using such definitions, *noisy* interactions are detected considering that if the user and the problem being solved belong to homologous sets, then the associated interaction category in matrix M^* should also belong to the same group of homologous sets. In other case, such interaction is considered as noisy and, therefore, it should be replaced with the interaction associated to the group of the corresponding user and item.

For this assumption, two groups of homologous sets are considered: the first one composed of the set of users $C1_p$, the set of problems $C1_u$, and the interaction $M^*[u, p] = 3$; the second one by the set of users $C2_p$, the set of problems $C2_u$, and the interaction $M^*[u, p] = 4$.

Equations 5 and 6 formalize how the matrix M^{**} is obtained, which is used afterwards to recommend.

$$M^*[u, p] = 3 \rightarrow M^{**}[u, p] = \begin{cases} \mathbf{4}, & \text{if } |C2_u| \geq 2|C1_u| \text{ and } |C2_p| \geq 2|C1_p| \\ \mathbf{3}, & \text{in other cases} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

$$M^*[u, p] = 4 \rightarrow M^{**}[u, p] = \begin{cases} \mathbf{3}, & \text{if } |C1_u| \geq 2|C2_u| \text{ and } |C1_p| \geq 2|C2_p| \\ \mathbf{4}, & \text{in other cases} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

3.3 Recommendation of Problems

This last step consists of the recommendation, which is supported by a traditional memory-based collaborative filtering paradigm [6]. This paradigm has been extended to work with matrix M^{**} . Let x be the active user that receives the recommendations, this step is composed of three phases: 1) Find his/her top k similar users using the matrix M^{**} , 2) Predict a score for each exercise not solved yet by user x using his/her similar users, and 3) Recommend exercises with the highest scores.

First, for each user x we build his/her profile, which is composed of his/her associated row in the matrix M^{**} . To find the top k similar users regarding x , the proposal uses a modification of the Simple Matching Coefficient (SMC) [2] to discard the influence of the interaction category $M^{**}[u, p] = 0$ in its calculation. This consideration is done because, when two users are compared, the common presence of a problem in the no solution attempts category does not indicate closeness. This modification is explained as follows.

Let S_{xu} be the set of problems where users x and u have the same interaction category, which is different from the zero category: $S_{xu} = \{p \mid M^{**}[u, p] = M^{**}[x, p] \text{ and } M^{**}[x, p] \neq 0\}$. Let D_{xu} be the set of problems where x or u have at least some interaction that is different from the zero category: $D_{xu} = \{p \mid M^{**}[u, p] \neq 0 \text{ or } M^{**}[x, p] \neq 0\}$. With these sets, the similarity between x and u is formulated as $sim(x, u) = S_{xu}/D_{xu}$.

Once the similarity values between x and all users are calculated, the users with the top k higher values are employed to calculate a score w_p for each problem p not solved by user x , as the sum of the similarities between x and each neighbour that solves p (Equation 7).

$$w_p = \sum_{u \in top-k(x)} sim(x, u) * M[u, p] \quad (7)$$

At last, the top- n problems with the highest scores w_p are recommended to the active user x .

4 Experimental Study

The evaluation of the proposal was performed by using a dataset obtained from the Caribbean Online Judge (2009-2010). This dataset is composed of 1910 users, 584 problems, and nearly 148000 user attempts to solve problems.

Using such dataset, the training and test sets were created following the procedure stated by Gunawardana and Shani [7]. For each user, solved problems were split in two sets adding at least one of them to the training set and the other to the test set. This strategy guarantees that both sets contain data from all users. Additionally, the experiments have been executed several times with different training-test partitions and their accuracy results have been averaged. The proposal also uses the information related with the unsuccessful attempts, which is stored independently to be used as input for each evaluation.

As evaluation measure, F1 measure is used, which evaluates the quality of the top n recommendation generation task [7]. F1 is defined in terms of precision and recall. In this context, precision is the amount of recommended problems that were solved, recall is the amount of solved problems that were recommended.

The experimental procedure was developed as follows. For each user the proposal generated a list of recommended problems considering the data in the training set. Such list and the solved problems in the test set were then used to obtain the F1 value for the current user. Finally, all users F1 values were averaged to obtain an overall F1 value that characterizes the proposal. Such procedure was repeated 10 times with various train-test partitions and the values were averaged. The proposal used the value $k = 130$ as the number of nearest neighbours used for computing the recommendations. Such value was adjusted through previous experimentation.

To evaluate the performance of our proposal, NN-OJ, in relation to previous works, we compare it to the works referred in Section 2.2 that are directly related to the current proposal. Specifically the researches in [18] (UCF-OJ, in Table 1), and in [21] (ICF-OJ, in Table 1) were used in the comparison. Additionally, in Table 1, the Binary approach is added to represent a procedure similar to the proposal, but using only matrix M .

Table 1 presents the results of the approaches evaluated for different number of top- n recommended problems, which are given in the range [5, 40]. The proposal outperforms the previous works for all sizes of the recommendation list. These results show that the matrix enrichment (Section 3.1) and the natural noise correction (Section 3.2) are procedures that imply an improvement of the recommendation accuracy in the POJ scenario.

	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40
NN-OJ	0.3875	0.3933	0.3784	0.3582	0.3397	0.3220	0.3055	0.2916
Binary	0.3614	0.3687	0.3540	0.3352	0.3189	0.3026	0.2895	0.2767
UCF-OJ	0.3833	0.3899	0.3736	0.3543	0.3367	0.3194	0.3035	0.2890
ICF-OJ	0.3602	0.3624	0.3494	0.3348	0.3191	0.3058	0.2932	0.2808

Table 1 F1 measure: NN-OJ vs. UCF-OJ, ICF-OJ and Binary

5 Conclusions

This contribution presents an approach for recommending problems to solve for supporting students in programming online judges. Specifically, the proposal is composed of two key steps: (i) the extended user-problem matrix enrichment and (ii) the natural noise management. These steps exploit the particularities of the data in POJs. This feature contrasts with previous works on POJs scenarios based on a direct application of typical recommendation techniques. The experimental procedure confirms the superiority of the current approach in relation with such previous works regarding the recommendation accuracy. Future works will be focused on managing the uncertainty inherent to the current scenario using fuzzy tools that allow a better representation of the information related to users behaviour.

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